

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 6 (2022)

PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

The Mediating Effect of Teachers' Trust on the Relationship Between Transformational Leadership of School Heads and Teachers' Self-Efficacy of Public School Teachers

Maricel P. Penonia^{1*}, Lyndon A. Quines¹

Article Information

Received: November 26, 2022

Accepted: December 01, 2022

Published: December 13, 2022

Keywords

*Educational Management,
Transformational Leadership,
Teachers' Self-Efficacy, Teachers'
Trust Mediating Effect, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

This study was to investigate the mediating role of teachers' trust in the relationship between transformational leadership of school leaders and teachers' self-efficacy among public school teachers in the Magsaysay North and South Districts. A stratified random sampling technique was used, which included 315 teachers as respondents. Through non-experimental quantitative mediation analysis utilizing path analysis, validated questionnaire, mean, regression techniques, and Pearson r , results showed significant relationships between transformational leadership of school heads and self-efficacy of teachers. There was no mediation on the impact of teachers' trust on the connection between transformational leadership and teachers' self-efficacy in public school teachers. Thus, teachers' trust is not one of the causes why transformational leadership of school heads can influence teachers' trust in public school teachers. It cannot account for the relationship between the two variables.

INTRODUCTION

With the high and increasing demand for education, teachers must have a considerable sense of self-efficacy since it is one of the driving forces that make an organization meet its goal and visions. Although self-efficacy may seem desirable, research and instructors' experiences indicate that its consequences are slightly more complex than they initially seem (Pajares, 2016). Due to its implications for teaching effectiveness, instructional methods, and learner academic achievement, teachers' self-efficacy has steadily taken on a more significant role in school psychology research (Klassen and Tze, 2017, 2019). In fact, during the past ten years, interest in teachers' self-efficacy has been rising, which is seen as an essential component of their drive to learn (Ross & Gray, 2016). A high level of self-efficacy for teachers is a stirring factor at work, helping them attain the triumph they wish while overcoming any blockades that may arise. They will also work harder with their pupils and look for new tactics to produce effective results (Ross & Gray, 2016). On the contrary, low self-efficacy people avoid complex tasks because they see them as a threat. Thus, they avoided setting goals, and as a result, their level of commitment was low (Kendra, 2020).

Furthermore, research that showed how crucial self-efficacy is for enhancing performance in the setting of organizations exists (Baker, 2001). According to several authors, what matters for employees' performance in organizations is that they will exert enough effort if it is well implemented since they believe they are highly effective (Qiu, Dooley, and Xie, 2020). On the other hand, personnel with poor self-efficacy are more likely to give up on the task before finishing it. Hence, a significant study has exposed that teachers with high levels of self-efficacy

experience higher levels of job satisfaction and lower levels of job-related stress and face fewer difficulties in managing students' misbehaviors. Hence, understanding the utmost backgrounds of self-efficacy might have vital payoffs in working for teachers' well-being and college effectiveness and development (Caprara *et al.*, 2018) since it anticipates expectations that one would prerequisite on the way to a process, what teachers transport to the classroom is taken into consideration to determine the level of their student's educational experiences, and thus the whole school and student success (Nelson, 2018; Ross & Gray, 2016). Teachers' sense of efficacy—also known as their “belief in their ability to frame and perform courses of action, required to accomplish a selected teaching mission specifically context”—has been recognized as one of the most operative features of their performance (Alvarez-Nunez, 2017; Chen & Yeung, 2015).

Teacher self-efficacy, on the other hand, is related to transformational leadership. In Serbia, transformational leadership and teacher self-efficacy were found to be self-determining predictors of collective efficacy in a study of 120 permanent secondary educators. Research exposed that individually focused transformational leadership significantly contributed to an elucidation of collective efficacy after specific predictor effects of group-focused dimensions of transformational leadership were controlled (Ninkovic & Knezobic Floric, 2018). Apart from this, transformational leadership and teacher trust is significantly connected. According to a study, building principals need to know more about the leadership philosophies that will increase teachers' efficacy and preparedness for change. Suppose they are aiming to effectively impact teachers in ways that go beyond developing trusted relationships with their staff.

¹ University of Mindanao, Philippines

* Corresponding author's e-mail: maricel.penonia001@deped.gov.ph

In that case, effective principals need to be able to include several leadership skills in their repertory (Fitzgerald, 2015). Lastly, self-efficacy and teachers' trust were also associated. A study on 746 teachers revealed simultaneous differences in teacher trust between schools. Also, self-efficacy, teachers' confidence, and collective efficacy were significantly correlated (Ball, 2015).

Effective organizations require both tactical and strategic thinking and trust-building by transformational leaders. In fact, there is a vast literature on transformational leadership and teachers' self-efficacy. Still, no study has been conducted yet on the mediating effect of teachers' trust between these variables, specifically in Magsaysay North and South Districts. Hence, there is an urgency to act on this study since there is no published research yet on the relationship between and among these three variables. To address this gap, the researcher is motivated to explore the connection between transformational leadership and teachers' self-efficacy with the mediation of teachers' trust.

Research Objective

The primary goal of this study was to determine how teacher trust mediated the association between public school teachers' self-efficacy and transformational leadership of school heads.

Particularly, the following objectives were developed:

1. To describe the level of transformational leadership in terms of:
 - Idealized influence,
 - Inspirational motivation,
 - Intellectual stimulation, and
 - Individualized consideration.
2. To determine the level of teachers' self-efficacy in terms of:
 - Instructional strategies,
 - Classroom management, and
 - Motivational strategies.
3. To measure the level of teachers' trust
4. To find out the significance of the relationship between:
 - Transformational leadership and teachers' self-efficacy,
 - Transformational leadership and teachers' trust, and
 - Teacher's trust and teachers' self-efficacy.
5. To determine the significance of teacher trust as a mediator in the relationship between public school teachers' self-efficacy and transformational leadership of school leaders.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents various approaches, points of view, theories, research and publication findings, and insightful observations from different authors pertinent to related study topics. It is essential to understand that this section provides considerable evidence to support the research aims. The independent variable is transformational leadership with the indicators; of idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and

individualized considerations (Nilwala, Gunawardana & Fernando, 2017). The dependent variable is teacher self-efficacy, with indicators of motivational strategies, instructional strategies, and classroom management (Nie, Lau & Liao, 2012). Teacher trust is mediating variable (Garcia-Ros, Hoy & Moran, 2003). Finally, the correlation between measures is about the relationship between transformational leadership and teachers' self-efficacy, transformational leadership and teachers' trust, and teachers' trust and teachers' self-efficacy. Thus, these three variables significantly impact this study because of the reliability of sources, dependability, and transferability.

Transformational Leadership of School Heads

In a globally increasing and multifaceted world, effective leadership is deemed necessary to retort issues of organizational failures. Hence, several studies have been conducted to check the various leadership style in multiple settings. The encouragement of progress and change in schools is a common theme in literary works about transformational leadership. As a result, how a leader manages their staff directly impacts how schools adapt and improve. The renowned authors of transformational leadership, James MacGregor Burns, Bernard M. Bass, Bruce J. Avolio, and Kenneth Leithwood, focused their studies on the origins and progress of this notion. To advance successful academic outcomes, transformational leadership is considered responsive to high school reform (Leithwood, & Jantzi, 2016; Leithwood & Jantzi, 2018; and Sun & Leithwood, 2017).

Additionally, educators who use transformational leadership techniques in the classroom inspire staff members to go above and beyond their individual goals and contribute to developing a shared vision and mission for the institution. Being committed to encouraging organizational members to grow and strengthening their commitment by raising their goals is the heart of transformational leadership. Individual consideration, inspirational motivation, idealized influence, and intellectual stimulation are all components of a transformational leadership type, which can be a leadership that prioritizes transformation (Derue, Nahrgan, Wellman & Humphrey, 2019; Nilwala, Gunawardana & Fernando, 2017).

Hence, idealized influence, also called charisma, is the primary indicator that the leader can exhibit authority and self-assurance, achieve reverence, and possess a strong sense of purpose. It is how followers view leaders as a result of their transforming behavior. It's one of the facets of transformational leadership. Idealized influence refers to the extent to which leaders are viewed as role models. Followers recognize and seek their leaders because they are appreciated, respected, and trusted by them (Bass *et al.*, 2003; Bass 2007; Moss & Ritossa, 2017).

Additionally, idealized influence has two manifestations: idealized influence conduct, in which leaders display good behavior and might even put their interests ahead of their workgroup's goals, and idealized influence attribute, in

which leaders are trusted and respected. It's a quality that has tremendous power and potential and is associated with charismatic individuals or leaders. Leaders with idealized influence also communicate in an animated or dramatic manner, engaging followers by making eye contact, leaning in toward the audience, or using lively facial expressions while retaining a comfortable posture. Leaders exhibit power and demonstrate through these non-verbal components of charismatic communication. These traits of charismatic speakers include appearing at ease and relaxed, conveying persuasive messages, coming across as pleasant and upbeat, and making inspiring arguments (Moss & Ritossa, 2017; Vertica and Vercicb, 2019). Furthermore, leaders who manifest idealized influence may motivate employees to reply to workplace mistreatment in ways that benefit themselves, others, and the organization. Employees were proud to be associated with their supervisors, and performance standards were created by the organization's goals regarding the idealized influence on employee performance (Bobocel & Zdaniuk, 2015; Chebon *et al.*, 2019). Hence, the second indicator, inspirational motivation, refers to motivating and pleasing supporters through communicative and persuasive interaction while displaying zeal, hopefulness, and confidence. It refers to the extent to which the school head pronounces an idea that appeals to and motivates supporters. In the long run, leaders are optimistic and act in ways that inspire others around them by giving their followers work purpose and a sense of challenge (Antonakis *et al.*, 2018; Judge & Piccolo, 2016). According to Kenyan research on the effect of inspiring motivation on employee performance, leaders spurred people to high productivity levels through creativity and invention. They ensured that messages were well communicated throughout the company (Chebon *et al.*, 2019).

Intellectual stimulation, the third indicator of transformational leadership, describes the extent to which the leaders arouse their follower's actions to be advanced and inventive and consider old organizational difficulties with a replacement viewpoint. It is defined as motivating the supporters to be progressive and innovative by questioning conventions, reframing problems, and treating old situations differently (Limsila & Ogunlana, 2018; Moss & Ritossa, 2017).

Thus, intellectual stimulation is probably the most frequently understudied facet of the transformational leadership method, yet it should significantly impact team dynamics, such as team learning. Leaders constantly challenge team members' beliefs and support novel and creative ways of acting to stimulate their minds and foster fresh thinking and doing (Rafferty & Griffin, 2020).

As a result, a study carried out in Puerto Rico discovered evidence of the substantial impact that leadership intellectual stimulation has on team learning and the optimistic team effect, as well as the ability of positive affect to drive team learning. The relationship between team learning and leadership intellectual stimulation is partially mediated by positive affect, which helps to

explain a sizable amount of additional variance. According to several academics, employee commitment to the firm directly results from intellectual stimulation. This, in turn, affects the organization's ability to adapt to achieve its objectives and support the dedication and effort of its staff (Anjali & Anand, 2015; Sanchez-Cardona *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, a study conducted in Kenya revealed a sturdy optimistic and significant association between intellectual stimulation leadership style and employee performance in SMEs. The study found that frontrunners that encourage their staff to apply critical thinking when solving difficulties they encounter at work take the initiative and look for creative ways to approach their work and assignments experience more excellent employee performance (Linge, Ogola, & Sikaliegh D. 2017). On the other hand, individualized consideration describes the extent to which leaders focus on the needs of each of their followers, delegate tasks that fit and boost employee motivation and abilities, encourage followers to take initiative, delegate complete control over a few clearly defined duties, and essentially serve as a mentor. Individualized consideration describes the extent to which leaders offer followers assistance, inspiration, and instruction. Hence, leaders should pay close attention to each follower's needs and assign specific tasks to help followers overcome personal obstacles (Bass *et al.*, 2003; Judge & Piccolo, 2016; Northouse, 2017; Yukl, 2016).

Including persons in a corporation's transformation process is considered individual consideration. These make it necessary to diagnose their demands correctly, wants, values, and abilities. Higher levels of trust in the leader result from this kind of activity. Therefore, in addition to the big picture, a transformational leader needs to understand what motivates each member of his team on an individual basis. Humans have a wide range of desires. Some people prefer money and a few leisure moments, while others seek excitement and change. The leader can employ all of those numerous demands in the proper method because they are aware of individuals' various needs and needs (Conger, 2014; Simic, 2018).

Similarly, transformational leaders establish recognition of individual differences and assign tasks in unison with their personal empathize. Following the progress in performing the individual studies, a frontrunner gets an image of regularity (or irregularity) of his action of individualized consideration (Bass & Avolio, 2009; Bass & Riggio, 2006; Conger, 2014; Simic, 2018). A study conducted in Kenya shows a strong positive and substantial association between individual consideration as a leadership style and employee performance. The study found that effective communication, self-development habits, encouragement of these practices, and mentoring and training are necessary for a leader to foster top performance (Linge, Ogola, & Sikaliegh, 2017). Thus, through creativity and innovation, leaders encouraged high productivity levels among their workforce and ensured that messages were well communicated throughout the company. When a

leader encourages workers to use their initiative, think critically about challenges they find while working, and look for creative ways to approach their job and tasks, they will perform better; when a leader encourages effective communication, self-development practices, self-confidence building, mentoring, and coaching, high-performance results (Bass 1985, 1998, 2007; Chebon *et al.*, 2019; Linge, Ogola, & Sikaliogh, 2017).

To summarize, transformational leadership and its elements—idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, individual consideration, and inspirational motivation—are frequently viewed as traits that enable a leader to articulately project a clear vision for the future and serve as an example for his followers. As a result, leaders who exhibit these qualities encourage their followers to identify with them and to be inspired and motivated. Employees were proud to be connected with their superiors, and performance standards were created in accordance with organizational needs, which speaks to the power of idealized influence on employee performance.

Teachers' Self-Efficacy

Teachers' self-efficacy foretells potential expectations towards a process; what teachers bring to the classroom is thought to determine the value of their student's educational experiences and overall school and student success. Hence, teachers' sense of efficacy—also known as their “confidence in their abilities to organize and execute courses of action required to accomplish a certain teaching assignment in a particular context” has been identified as one of the most effective characteristics of their performance. Thus, the indicators of teacher self-efficacy were instructional strategies, classroom management, and motivational strategies (Alvarez-Nunez, 2017, Chen & Yeung, 2015; Nelson, 2018; Ross & Gray, 2016; Tschannen-Moran, & Hoy, 2017).

Moreover, instructional self-efficacy was “personal beliefs about one's capacity to assist students in learning.” Accordingly, the teacher's engagement, perseverance, and effort with pupils should be influenced by their level of instructional self-efficacy. According to this notion, teachers must have faith in their capacity to improve learning if they want students to learn effectively since students may not know well if they lack confidence in their ability to teach. Thus, low self-efficacy teachers might not plan or prepare their lesson plans. Consequently, teacher effectiveness affects how well children learn (Henson, 2020; Schunk, 2012; Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2017;).

Additionally, teachers must employ diverse pedagogical strategies to engage pupils in learning. The mechanisms of teaching, often known as instructional methods, concern how teachers instruct students during the teaching process. Instruction is the relationship between the pupils and the subject of the lesson. Teachers can organize and prepare their work to fulfill the demands of their student's learning when they are familiar with various teaching techniques. Planning and preparation, familiarity with their instructional resources, a well-

defined pedagogy, selecting their educational goals, and evaluating pupils while they teach are all characteristics of effective teachers (Tournaki, Lyublinskaya, & Carolan, 2019). However, teachers who enter the profession for job security may not take much ownership in planning and preparation, which causes issues. Effective teachers' lessons might be seen as “scaffolded,” assisting students in achieving goals. Without the assistance of good teachers, learners might not reach their learning objectives. According to the scaffolding metaphor, the process of learning can be described as “mediated by an expert helping a beginner through a task to guarantee the learner gets the expert's skills.”

One of the elements of successful teaching that teachers can employ to encourage students in their learning and effectively engage them in tasks is “scaffolding students' task involvement” (Brophy, 2016).

Meanwhile, teachers who use effective instructional strategies demonstrate their mastery of the subject matter and abilities that need to be taught in light of the social goals of education. According to this author, teaching is the act of imparting knowledge and skills to students, and for this to happen, a teacher needs to be familiar with the subject matter. Conferring to several scholars, there is a considerable difference between the academic achievement of students taught using inquiry and demonstration tactics instead of debate and lecture strategies. Hence, to improve teaching and learning, teachers must use diverse instructional techniques (Darling-Hammond & Baratz-Snowden 2016; Onweh & Akpan 2014). Classroom Management - the second indicator of teachers' self-efficacy assesses how confident teachers are in their ability to handle classroom management, housekeeping, and other concerns that are relevant to the classroom. It is crucial to the teacher efficacy construct as a place where teachers will feel effective in assisting pupils in learning. Experts in classroom management are thought to be effective teachers. Consequently, teachers' perceived classroom management characteristics were favorably correlated with their classroom management self-efficacy, especially during their early careers (Lazarides *et al.*, 2020). However, teachers often think it's hard to learn classroom management, one of the components of teacher efficacy. Other educational levels experience the same problem. Teachers use different tactics to manage disruptive behavior in the classroom. The academic community prioritizes such control to enhance learning (Lewis, Romi, Qui, & Katz, 2017).

Additionally, teachers seeing pupils engaging in problematic behaviors like bullying find it challenging to accomplish their instructional objectives. Seeing the teacher's expertise in a vast class could be difficult. Several researchers contended that while massive courses “accommodate” many students, connections rob pupils of learning opportunities. According to these researchers, the lack of rapport that students experience with the teacher and other students in large classes can deter students from being motivated to participate in

the learning process. Effective educators may serve as mediators in their interactions with students to aid in the learning process (Yazedjian & Kolkhorst, 2017).

The third indicator of a teacher's self-efficacy, motivational strategies, describes how the teacher encourages or involves the student in the learning process. It is crucial to the teacher efficacy concept since it is here that teachers will believe they can effectively support students' learning. The instructors' motivation can also affect their efforts in the classroom, mainly in how they select their "activities, degree of effort, and tenacity with students" (Ware & Kitsantas, 2017). Research has demonstrated a connection between teacher efficacy and "performance, commitment, and professional retention." There has been a growing interest in teacher self-efficacy in the past ten years as it is viewed as a crucial component of their overall job motivation. A high level of self-efficacy is a motivating factor for teachers at work, causing them to achieve the success they desire, overcome any challenges that may arise, work harder with their pupils, and look for new approaches to produce fruitful results. The most crucial element of education is engaging students in their learning because this is the only way to meet their learning objectives.

The instructor must function as a facilitator for the student's activities and hold effective beliefs that will inspire student learning. The ability of a teacher to achieve the appropriate levels of student engagement and learning, even with challenging or unmotivated students, is measured by their efficacy belief. Such views are associated with high teacher efficacy, which has a bearing on student achievement. The effectiveness of teachers, institutional identity, and motivating techniques all significantly and favorably influence students' progress in L2 (Karimi & Nikbakht, 2019).

Teacher Trust

The word "Trust" is frequently used in the literature on educational reform and is consistently cited as one of the critical components of such transformation. Despite the significance of trust, there is not a lot of systematic research on it in educational backgrounds, particularly in public schools. According to findings from earlier studies, a school's daily operations are greatly facilitated by trust among staff members. Trust is also a valuable resource for principals as they go on board with their ambitious improvement plans. Also, faith is one of the key differences between effective and ineffective schools. Generally, trust is typically conceptualized by researchers studying organizational behavior as belief in and allegiance to the leader (Bryk & Schneider, 2020; Ngodo, 2018). Moreover, other authors assert that this definition of trust has many facets, including goodwill (the belief that a trusted party will look out for one's best interests), dependability (the degree to which one could depend on other individuals or groups), competency (the degree to which another person or group is competent), honesty, and transparency (the degree to which no information is

kept a secret from others). This definition has frequently been the starting point for studies on trust in educational settings. It is, therefore, the most crucial component in increasing learning and fostering connections. It is created by devoting time and providing structure to trust-building activities like recognizing and encouraging others, and it is ingrained in the institution's ethos (Brown 2014; Hoy and Tschannen-Moran 2017). In addition, four components make up students' trust in schools. Among these factors, teacher confidence in the principal is crucial and cited as the foundation of school trust. It is thought that teachers' readiness to rely on the principal, who is dependable, kind, honest, and trustworthy, is the foundation of their trust in the principal, colleagues, students, and parents. Having faith in the principal to maintain their word and act in the teachers' best interests is called having trust in the principal (Tschannen-Moran, 2000, 2017).

Hence, teachers assume they can rely on the principal's words, deeds, and written or spoken statements. Teachers' and followers' faith in the principal or leader is directly influenced by circumstances where sensitive and apparent transformational leadership is present. Therefore, any endeavor to change education and enhance student accomplishment is credited to the critical function of interpersonal relationships and trust (Bass & Riggio, 2016; Dirks & Ferrin, 2020; Gillespie & Mann, 2014; Jung & Avolio, 2000 and Tschannen-Moran, 2017).

Thus, specific research findings support the notion that the caliber of student-teacher interactions strongly influences student involvement. According to one study, students' judgments of their level of class participation accounted for about half of the difference in their teacher's closeness-trust scores. A qualitative study showed that a variety of factors, including personal, instructor-related, course-related, and elements connected to the classroom environment, explain the poor student involvement in classes. They discovered two of the teachers' related reasons—instructors' inability to establish a strong relationship with students and instructors' poor teaching abilities—were the biggest influences on personal and classroom environment-related reasons. Accordingly, it was anticipated that there would be a strong correlation between students' level of engagement and their trust in their lecturers (Sad & Zer, 2014).

In summary, there hasn't been much systematic study on trust in educational environments, specifically public schools, over the past few decades. Hence, according to findings from earlier studies, trust between individuals within a school facilitates much of a school's daily operation and is a crucial resource as principals launch ambitious enhancement campaigns. In general, faith is one of the distinguishing features separating effective schools from those that are not. Accordingly, today's educators need a lot of teacher trust to get good outcomes. Hence, the only way for school leaders to do this is through transformational leadership. In addition, to build teachers' trust, it is essential for instructors to feel very practical. The material on transformational

leadership, teacher self-efficacy, and teacher confidence support the idea that it affects teachers' performance. It is essential, according to researchers, in managing a school and achieving successful goals. Additionally, when teachers are content and joyful, they are more driven to work hard and complete tasks successfully under the direction of a transformational leader. Therefore, this study aims to ascertain if teachers' trust mediates the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and the transformational leadership of school leaders. With teachers' trust as another predictor of transformational leadership on teachers' self-efficacy, it adds flavor to how to deal with problems with teachers' self-efficacy.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative approach, using a correlation technique design to assess the relationship between transformational leadership and teachers' self-efficacy, transformational leadership and teachers' trust, and teachers' trust and teachers' self-efficacy. Descriptive non-experimental correlational design controlled the extent of a relationship between two or more variables (Goertzen, 2017). In this study, the correlation method is the best design to meet the study's objectives and find out whether the hypothesis is accepted. Now, if the significance value is more significant than .05, then it means that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. Hypothesis testing determines if the correlations can be strong or weak (Creswell, 2012). Since it evaluated the degrees of transformational leadership exhibited by school leaders as well as teacher self-efficacy and teacher trust in the public elementary schools in the Magsaysay North and South District, the study was descriptive. This study was correlational since it used the survey questionnaire to collect the primary data. It looked at the connections between transformational leadership, teacher self-efficacy, and teacher trust.

The study sought to understand the relationships between transformational leadership and teacher self-efficacy, transformational leadership and teacher confidence, teacher trust and teacher self-efficacy, and the mediating role of teacher trust in the relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and teachers' self-efficacy of public elementary schools in Magsaysay North and South District. Moreover, this study utilized the testing of mediation to investigate the three variables in this study. In other words, it assessed the relationship between the predictor and the mediator variables and the relationship between the mediator and

the criterion variables (Baron and Kenny, 1986). According to a straightforward mediation model, the relationship between an independent variable and an outcome that is observed can be explained by the influence of a third factor, or mediator. When the direct link between the independent variable and the result is eliminated after the mediator's power has been considered, the relationship is said to be fully mediated. When the mediator explains some but not all of the relationship between the independent variable and the result, this is referred to as partial mediation. The indirect effect is the measure of mediation (Baron and Kenny, 1986). Thus, mediation analysis is not limited to linear regression but also logistic or polynomial regression and more (Shrout and Bolger, 2002).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data attained from the participants on transformational leadership, teachers' self-efficacy and teachers' trust are presented, analyzed and interpreted in this section based on the research objectives previously stated. The order of discussions on the mentioned topic is as follows: level of transformational leadership; level of teacher self-efficacy; level of teacher trust; correlations between transformational leadership and teacher self-efficacy; correlations between transformational leadership and teacher trust; and correlation between teacher self-efficacy and teacher trust.

Level of Transformational Leadership

Shown in Table 1 is the level of Transformational Leadership. The standard deviation was less than 1.00 which means there is consistency of responses among respondents. The overall mean score was 4.05 described as high. Particularly, the level of transformational leadership of school heads on the four indicators were as follows: idealized influence garnered a mean of 4.25 defined as very high, intellectual stimulation has a mean of 4.03 with a descriptive level of high, inspirational motivation has a mean of 3.91 characterized as high and individualized consideration which scored 4.00 likewise, was labelled as high. Data showed that the school heads had manifested very good command of transformational leadership in terms of idealized influence which indicates that leaders help others develop themselves. The data showed that transformational leadership in terms of intellectual stimulation was manifested at all times. This is an indicative of their very high satisfaction when his subordinates meet agreed-upon standards. Likewise,

Table 1: Level of Transformational Leadership

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Idealized Influence	0.48	4.25	Very High
Intellectual Stimulation	0.50	4.03	High
Inspirational Motivation	0.58	3.91	High
Individualized Consideration	0.56	4.00	High
Overall	0.46	4.05	High

the level of transformational leadership of teachers in terms of individualized consideration was high, which indicates that the respondents are agreeing to the fact that the leadership skill in terms of helping them develop themselves, letting them know what they are doing and giving personal attention to others who seem rejected is manifested most of the time. Lastly, the data reflected that transformational leadership of school heads in terms of inspirational motivation was manifested most of the time which means that the leader's influence among its subordinates was high.

Level of Teachers' Self-Efficacy

Revealed in Table 2 is the level of self-efficacy of public elementary schools in Magsaysay North and South District. The overall mean score was 4.42 labeled as very high. Particularly, the level of self-efficacy on the following indicators were as follows: motivational strategies has a mean of 4.51 with an interpretation of very high, instructional strategies has a mean of 4.41 labeled as very high and classroom management has a mean of 4.34 characterized as very high. Data reflects the very high level of self-efficacy in terms of

Table 2: Level of Self-efficacy

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Motivational Strategies	0.46	4.51	Very High
Classroom Management	0.48	4.34	Very High
Instructional Strategies	0.47	4.41	Very High
Overall	0.42	4.42	Very High

motivational strategies which means that the teacher has helped the students value learning manifested at all times. Furthermore, it was observed that instructional strategies were observed as very high which describes as teacher providing an alternative explanation or example when students are confused was always manifested. Lastly, the data revealed that the teacher's level of self-efficacy in terms of classroom management was very high. It showed that teachers were able to get students to follow classroom rules.

Level of Teacher Trust

Shown in Table 3 is the level of teacher trust of public elementary school teachers in Magsaysay North and South District. 3.59 described as high was the overall mean score. This implies that the teacher trust is manifested most of the time. Particularly, the level of teacher trust on the following items were as follows: teachers in this school are showing concern for their students has a mean of 4.39 which has an equivalent descriptive level of very high; acting with the best interest of teachers in mind has a mean of 4.29 which means very high; teachers in this school is trusting the principal has a mean of 4.28 which means very high; teacher in this school is doing their jobs well has a mean of 4.23 which means very high; the principal is competent in doing his or her job has a mean of 4.22 which means very high; having faith in the integrity of the principal has a mean of 4.16 which has a descriptive level of high; teachers in this school are believing in each other has a mean of 4.16 which has a descriptive level of high; even in difficult situation teachers in this school can depend in each other has a mean of 4.16 which means high; teachers in this school are being reliable has a mean of 4.10 which means high; teachers in this school are trusting in each other and having faith in the integrity of their colleagues have means of 4.09 which means high; teachers in this school are open with each other has a mean of 4.08 which has a descriptive level of high; teachers in this school is typically looking out for each

other has a mean of 4.04 which means high; teachers in this school are counting for parental support has a mean of 4.02 which means high; having students in this school who can be counted on has a mean of 4.01 which means high; teachers in this school are relying on the principal has a mean of 3.99 which means high; having students in this school who are reliable has a mean of 3.97 which means high; teachers are feeling comfortable admitting to the principal they have made a mistake got a mean score of 3.95 and described as high; students in this school are caring for each other got a mean score of 3.95 which is described as high; teachers in this school are trusting their students has a mean score of 3.95 and described as high when the principal is committing to something teachers can be sure it is getting done has a mean score of 3.91 and described as high; the principal of this school is keeping his or her word has a mean score of 3.89 which is described as high; teachers are thinking that most of the parents are doing a good job has a mean of 3.87 which is described as high; students in this school are being reliable in their commitment has a mean score of 3.86 and it is described as high; if I had a school-age child, I would comfortably put my own child in most of anyone's classroom in this school has a mean score of 3.86 and the descriptive level is high; having students in this school who have to be closely supervised has a mean score of 3.83 and the descriptive level is high; having students in this school who can be counted on their work has a mean score of 3.83 and it is described as high; when teachers in this school is telling you something you can believe it has a mean score of 3.78 and it is described as high; the principal is openly sharing personal information with teachers has a mean score of 3.78 which has a descriptive level of high; the students in this school are talking freely about their lives outside the school has a mean score of 3.72 and described as high; teachers are guarded on what they say to parents has a mean score of 3.50 and described as high; teachers in this school is believing what their student say has a mean score of 3.46 which

has a descriptive level of high; teachers in this school are not sharing much of their lives outside the school has a mean score of 3.31 and described as moderate; teachers here are only trusting teachers in their clique has a mean score of 3.17 and described as moderate; students in this school are cheating if they have a chance has a mean score of 3.01 and got a descriptive level of moderate; having students who are secretive has a mean score of 2.98 and got a descriptive level of moderate; teachers in

this school are often questioning the motive of the school has a mean score of 2.81 and got a descriptive level of moderate; teachers in this school are being suspicious of their students has a mean score of 2.78 and got a descriptive level of moderate; teachers in this school are being suspicious parent's motive has a mean score of 2.74 and got a descriptive level of moderate; teachers are taking unfair advantage of each other in this school has a mean score of 2.61 and described as moderate; the principal is

Table 3: Level of Teacher Trust

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
The principal is being unresponsive to teacher's concern.	1.23	2.59	Low
Teachers in this school are relying on the principal.	0.82	3.99	High
The teachers in this school are trusting the principal.	0.69	4.28	Very High
The principal in this school typically is acting with the best interest of teachers in mind.	0.71	4.19	High
The principal of this school is not showing concern for teachers.	1.22	2.34	Low
The principal is not really telling teachers what's going on.	1.18	2.53	Low
The principal in this school is keeping his or her word.	0.878	3.89	High
The principal is taking unfair advantage of teachers in this school.	1.19	2.53	Low
Teachers in this school are having faith in the integrity of the principal.	0.71	4.16	High
Teachers in this school are being suspicious of most of the principal's action.	1.16	2.58	Low
Teachers in this school are often questioning the motives of the principal.	1.18	2.81	Moderate
The principal openly is sharing personal information with teachers.	0.92	3.72	High
When the principal is committing to something teachers can be sure it is getting done.	0.74	3.91	High
The principal in this school is being competent in doing his or her job.	0.76	4.22	Very High
Teachers are feeling comfortable admitting to the principal they have made a mistake.	0.73	3.95	High
Teachers in this school are believing in each other.	0.70	4.16	High
Even in difficult situations, teachers in this school are depending on each other.	0.68	4.16	High
Teachers in this school are being open with each other.	0.76	4.08	High
When teachers in this school is telling you something, you can believe it.	0.71	3.78	High
Teachers in this school is typically looking out for each other.	0.68	4.04	High
Teachers in this school are trusting each other.	0.70	4.09	High
Teachers in this school are having faith in the integrity of their colleagues.	0.68	4.09	High
Teachers here only are trusting teachers in their clique.	1.04	3.17	Moderate
If I had a school-age child, I would comfortably be putting my own child in most anyone's classroom in this school.	0.79	3.86	High
Teachers are taking unfair advantage of each other in this school.	1.07	2.61	Moderate
Teachers in this school are being suspicious with each other.	1.08	2.52	Low
Teachers in this school are being reliable.	0.67	4.10	High
Teachers in this school are doing their jobs well.	0.64	4.23	Very High
Teachers in this school are not sharing much of their lives outside the school.	0.94	3.31	Moderate
Having students in this school who are reliable.	0.66	3.97	High
Having students in this school who can be counted on.	0.63	4.01	High
Teachers are thinking that most of the parents do a good job.	0.67	3.87	High
Having students in this school who have to be closely supervised.	0.75	3.83	High
Students in this school are being reliable in their commitments.	0.65	3.86	High
Teachers in this school are trusting their students.	0.67	3.92	High
Students in this school are caring each other.	0.64	3.95	High

Teachers in this school are counting on the parental support.	0.65	4.02	High
Having students who are secretive.	0.99	2.98	Moderate
Students in this school are cheating if they have a chance.	0.97	3.01	Moderate
Having students in this school who can be counted on their work.	0.62	3.83	High
Teachers in this school are being suspicious of their students.	1.03	2.78	Moderate
Teachers are avoiding making contacts with parents.	1.16	2.52	Low
Teachers in this school are showing concern for their students.	0.67	4.39	Very High
Teachers are being suspicious of parent's motives.	1.03	2.74	Moderate
Teachers in this school are believing what's their students say.	0.71	3.46	High
Teachers in this school are trusting parents.	0.67	4.03	High
The students in this school are talking freely about their lives outside the school.	0.74	3.72	High
Teachers are being guarded in what they say to parents.	0.76	4.22	Very High
Overall	0.40	3.59	High

being unresponsive to teachers concern has a mean score of 2.59 with a descriptive level of low; teachers in this school are being suspicious of most of the principal's action has a mean score of 2.58 and described as low; the principal is not really telling teachers what's going on has a mean score of 2.53 and got a descriptive level of low; teachers in this school are being suspicious with each other got a mean score of 2.52 with a descriptive level of low; teachers are avoiding contacts with parents got a mean score of 2.52 with a descriptive level of low; the principal in this school is not showing concern for teachers with a mean score of 2.34 and it is described as low. Nevertheless, it can be inferred that the school has considered to build trust relationship between the school heads and teachers. Also, the school made all the possible efforts to establish rapport and create a structure of trust-building space.

Moreover, it can be gleaned that the school heads have won the trust and confidence of the teachers and is acting with the best interest of the teachers. Respondents believed that school leaders manage day to day activities conducive to the formation of trust and confidence to school stakeholders. Furthermore, it can be inferred that trust-relationship in the school is manifested most of

the time. The school heads are able to recognize their personal impact on establishing rapport thus, establishing effective working relationships with other school heads, teachers, parents and members of the community.

Correlations between Transformational Leadership and Self-efficacy

The findings of the test to determine the association between transformational leadership and self-efficacy are shown in Table 4. The association was examined at 0.05 level of significance in accordance with the hypothesis. The null hypothesis was rejected by the overall r-value of .489 and the p-value of 0.05. It implies that transformative leadership and teacher self-efficacy have a substantial link. This suggests a relationship between teacher self-efficacy and the transformative leadership of school leaders.

Distinctively, result disclosed that indicators of transformational leadership are positively correlated on self-efficacy, since the p-value is <0.05 and the overall r-value is .438 on idealized influence, .453 on intellectual stimulation, .395 on inspirational motivation, and .421 on individualized consideration. Data revealed transformational leadership of school heads and self-efficacy of teachers is positively associated.

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Transformational Leadership and Self-Efficacy

Transformational Leadership	Self-Efficacy			
	Motivational Strategies	Classroom Management	Instructional Strategies	Overall
Idealized Influence	.340*(0.000)	.424*(0.000)	.420*(0.000)	.438*(0.000)
Intellectual Stimulation	.363*(0.000)	.449*(0.000)	.412*(0.000)	.453*(0.000)
Inspirational Motivation	.322*(0.000)	.394*(0.000)	.352*(0.000)	.395*(0.000)
Individualized Consideration	.329*(0.000)	.419*(0.000)	.389*(0.000)	.421*(0.000)
Overall	.388*(0.000)	.484*(0.000)	.450*(0.000)	.489*(0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Furthermore, data shows that all indicators of self-efficacy are positively correlated on transformational leadership, since the p-value is <0.05 and the overall r-value is .388 on

motivational strategies, .484 on classroom management and, .450 on instructional strategies, Hence the two variables are positively associated.

Correlations between Transformational Leadership and Teacher Trust

The findings of the experiment testing the correlation between transformative leadership and teacher trust are shown in Table 5. As shown in the table, there is a positive correlation between the indicators of transformational leadership and teacher trust, with an overall r-value of .522 and a p-value of 0.05 signifying the rejection of the null hypothesis. It implies that transformative leadership and teachers’ trust are significantly related.

Specifically, in the indicator idealized influence, data show that it has a positive correlation with teacher trust because of its computed r-value is .358 with a p-value <0.05. The p-value result means that there is a relationship between the idealized influence of transformational leadership and trust of the respondents; teacher trust needs idealized influence in transformational leadership. Also, the other indicator which is intellectual stimulation has an r-value of .497 with a p-value <0.05. This shows that intellectual stimulation is positively associated with teacher trust.

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Transformational Leadership and Teacher Trust

Transformational Leadership	Teacher Trust Overall
Idealized Influence	.358*(0.000)
Intellectual Stimulation	.497*(0.000)
Inspirational Motivation	.500*(0.000)
Individualized Consideration	.446*(0.000)
Overall	.522*(0.000)

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.*

Besides, inspirational motivation got an r-value of .500 with a p-value <0.05. which shows that inspirational motivation is needful in teacher trust. Last but not least indicator is individualized consideration which has an r-value of .446 with a p-value <0.05 which shows that individualized consideration indicates strong relationship of execution on teacher trust. In short, it is a useful tool in attaining teacher trust.

significance, as stated in the hypothesis. Data for the indicator of motivating techniques indicate a favorable correlation between them and self-efficacy. The p-value is 0.05 and the r-value is .237. This demonstrates how motivating techniques affect teachers’ perceptions of their own efficacy. It is crucial to the teacher efficacy concept because it determines how effectively teachers can support students’ learning.

Correlations between Teacher Trust and Self-Efficacy

The findings of the test to determine the association between teacher trust and self-efficacy are displayed in Table 6. The association was examined at 0.05 level of

Likewise, the other indicator which is classroom management has an r-value of .276 with a p-value of <0.05. This shows that classroom management is positively associated with self-efficacy. This implies that school heads play a big part in achieving teachers’ trust.

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between the Teacher Trust and Self-Efficacy

Teacher Trust	Self-Efficacy			
	Motivational Strategies	Classroom Management	Instructional Strategies	Overall
Overall	.237*(0.000)	.276*(0.000)	.285*(0.000)	.295*(0.000)

Lastly, criteria for instructional leadership also showed a positive correlation to teacher self-efficacy with an r-value of .285 with a p-value of <0.05. This further means that criteria for instructional strategies contributed a big part in the facets of teacher self-efficacy. Hence, instructional strategies showed high relationship with teacher trust.

The total result showed a positive correlation between self-efficacy and teacher trust, with an overall r-value of .295 and a p-value of <0.05. Therefore, the assumption that there is no meaningful association between teacher self-efficacy and teacher trust was rejected.

data in this table. This table presents the direct effect of transformational leadership on self-efficacy, teacher trust and self-efficacy and transformational leadership on self-efficacy. Transformational Leadership and Teacher Trust is the path a coefficient which has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .454, standardized regression coefficient of .522, SE of .042 and a probability value less than 0.05. Below the significance level of 0.05 implies that these two variables have a significant relationship and low or small standard error means that the estimate is more precise. Besides, the effect size or the impact of transformational leadership on teachers’ trust is 45 %. Thus, the path b coefficient is Teacher Trust and Self-Efficacy which has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .058, standardized regression coefficient of .055, SE of .062 and a p-value of .344 which is more than 0.05 which means there is a strong conclusion to

On The Mediating Effect of Teacher Trust

The path analysis on the mediator role of teacher trust in the connection between transformational leadership and teacher self-efficacy is displayed in Table 7. The findings of the SPSS AMOS were used to compile the

Table 7: Mediating Effect: Path Analysis (No Mediation)

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
TL TT	.454	.522	.042	10.832	***
TT SE	.058	.055	.062	.948	.343
TL SE	.428	.461	.054	7.998	***

say that Teacher Trust and Self-efficacy are not significant. The effect size of teacher trust on self-efficacy is 6%. And lastly, path c coefficient shows the effect size of transformational leadership on self-efficacy. The data result has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .428 or 43% efficacy, standardized regression coefficient of .461; the computed standard error is .054 and a p-value less than 0.05 which means that it is significant. Mathematically, this supports the assumption that transformational leadership is associated with self-efficacy.

X = TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP (TL)
 Y = SELF-EFFICACY (SE)
 M = TEACHER TRUST (TT)

Figure 3: Regression Weights on the Mediating Effect of Teacher Trust on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Self-Efficacy

In addition, Figure 3 depicts the result of the mediating effect computation. It shows the effect size of path correlation coefficients of the three variables used in this study. At the 0.05 level, the route analysis gave a p value of less than 0.05, which is significant. This suggests that teacher trust has role in the relationship between transformational leadership and teachers’ trust among public school elementary teachers. Furthermore, at the conclusion of teacher trust, the mediator variable, the causal association between transformational leadership and self-efficacy has been lowered from a significant beta coefficient value of .489 to .43, which is still significant. The raw correlation between transformational leadership and teachers’ trust has a total impact of .489. The extent of the association between transformational leadership and self-efficacy with teacher trust included in the regression is represented by the direct effect value of .43. The indirect value of 0.027 represents the amount of original link between transformational leadership and teachers’ self-efficacy that has been transferred to teacher

trust. The formula is: (a*b), where “a” is the path between the independent and mediator variables, “b” denotes the path between the mediator and dependent variables. Moreover, assessed significance of the indirect effect is found to be not significant. Thus, it is continued to look for the significance of the indirect effect (c’) and the direct effect shows a positive standardized coefficient of .52 which means significant. Therefore, the conclusion is no mediation following the steps of mediation analysis by Zhao *et al.* (2010). Then, the indirect effect must be divided by the total effect to get the ratio index; in this case, 0.027 divided by .489 equals 0.0552. Thus, the final correlation contends that teachers’ trust carries no influence on the relationship between transformational leadership and teachers’ self-efficacy. Therefore, the research study falls under no mediation.

In addition, three conditions must be met for a third variable to operate as a mediator (Baron and Kenny, 1986). These are classified as Steps 1 through 3 in Table 7. The fourth and last step is. In Step 1 (Path c), self-efficacy, the dependent variable, is significantly predicted by transformational leadership, the independent variable (IV) (DV). Transformational leadership (IV) significantly predicts teacher trust in step 2 (Path a), and the mediator (MV). Teacher trust (MV) strongly predicts self-efficacy in step 3 (Path b). Similar to this, the aim of steps 1 through 3 is to prove the existence of zero-order correlations between variables. And since there are no association factors on which to base the process of calculating relationships, we can automatically draw the conclusion that mediation is not likely. Furthermore, one must move on to step 4 if steps 1 through 3 reveal a significant relationship. The combined impact of transformative leadership and teacher trust on teachers’ self-efficacy is thus still considerable in step 4.

Further path analysis of the mediation effect using AMOS SPSS is required as a matter of triangulation to determine the relevance of the intervening variable. Additionally, if the effect of the IV on the DV stops being significant towards the end of the analysis, full mediation will be attained. The mediating variable is a mediator of all effects, according to this evidence. If the regression coefficient is drastically diminished but still significant at the final step, then partial mediation has been achieved. This indicates that while some of the IV is mediated by the MV, other portions are either direct or mediated by other variables outside the scope of the model. In this instance, limiting MV (teachers’ trust) greatly reduces the impact of the IV (transformational leadership) on DV (self-efficacy). As a result, since the

effect is not considerable, there was no mediation. With the use of Baron and Kenny's steps in testing mediation of teacher trust, the researcher proved that mediation is significant and there is partial mediation. First, conduct a simple regression analysis with X predicting M to test for path a- the independent variable or X (transformational leadership) affects the mediator or M (teacher trust) at beta coefficient of .45 with a SE of .21 and the relationship is significant at 0.05 significance level. Second, conduct a simple regression analysis with M predicting Y to test for the significance of path b-the mediating variable or M (teacher trust) affects the dependent variable or D (self-efficacy) at beta coefficient of .06, where teacher trust got a residual error of .12 and the relationship is significant at 0.05 significance level. Third, conduct a simple regression analysis with X predicting Y to test for the significance of path c- the independent variable or X (transformational leadership) affects the dependent variable or Y (self-efficacy) at beta coefficient of .43, where organizational culture has a residual error 2 of .14 and the relationship is significant at 0.05 significance level. Last but not least, after controlling the dependent variable or Y (self-efficacy) as predicted by independent variable or X (transformational leadership) and including the mediating variable or M (teacher trust) as a predictor of teachers' self-efficacy it is regressed to .43.

Though the alpha level is still significant at 0.05 significance level of transformational leadership and self-efficacy but statistically no mediation has been found in this study. Since it has no mediation, it could be claimed that teacher trust does not play a significant role in transformational leadership in its influence in teachers' self-efficacy. This indicates that teacher trust is not one of the reasons how transformational leadership influences teachers' self-efficacy.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are formulated based on the findings of the study. There is strong evidence to reject the null hypotheses in favor of the alternative views. Moreover, a high level of transformational leadership, a very high level of teacher self-efficacy, and a high level of teacher trust were discovered among the responder public school teachers. The research findings also reveal a strong correlation between transformational leadership and teacher self-efficacy in the school. Similarly, there is a positive correlation between transformational leadership and teacher trust. Thus, there is a strong link between teacher self-efficacy and teacher trust.

Lastly, the study's findings imply that teacher trust does not influence the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational culture. The straightforward cause-and-effect relationship between transformational leadership and teacher self-efficacy is uninfluenced by mediating variable teachers' trust. The findings demonstrated that even with the absence of teacher trust, the effect of transformational leadership on teacher self-efficacy is still evident.

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